

FCC-ee Socio-economic benefits

Context

This work has been carried out in the frame of the EU co-funded H2020 project "Future Circular Collider Innovation Study" (FCCIS). The goal is to plan for a sustainable Future Circular Collider scenario by identifying and analysing the socio-economic impact potentials and developing strategies and plans to incorporate them in the FCC scenario development from the onset. The socio-economic impact estimates rely on a working hypothesis of the resources engaged for the FCC project. Therefore, the work includes total project cost estimates. The FCCIS project is an integral part of the overall international FCC Feasibility Study hosted by CERN.

This document summarises the results of the second version of the report and reflects new evidence and assessment carried out between September 2024 and April 2025.

Benefits in figures

	Share of the total	Not discounted	Discounted
TOTAL COSTS (MCHF)	100%	38,308	20,020
INVESTMENTS (CAPEX)	50.8%	16,215	10,171
OPERATION COSTS (OPEX)	47.1%	21,212	9,423
PERSONNEL COSTS		16,802	7,544
OTHER OPERATIONAL COSTS		4,410	1,879
NEGATIVE EXTERNALITIES	1.7%	653	354
SHADOW COST OF CARBON*		633	341
SOCIAL COST OF IONISING RADIATION		1.3	0.6
SOCIAL COST OF PROJECT-RELATED INDUCED NOISE		0.02	0.02
LOSS OF AGRICULTURAL INCOME, BIODIVERSITY & HABITAT		8	4
SOCIAL COST OF PROJECT-RELATED TRAFFIC-INDUCED AIR POLLUTION		1	1
SOCIAL COST OF PROJECT-RELATED TRAFFIC-INDUCED GHG EXTERNALITIES		10	7
DECOMMISSIONING COSTS**	0.4%	228	72
TOTAL CORE BENEFITS (MCHF)	100%	57,244	24,092
SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION	11.7%	6,515	2,817
EARLY CAREER RESEARCHER TRAINING	20.7%	20,687	4,986
INDUSTRIAL BENEFITS FOR SUPPLIERS	39.7%	17,577	9,569
OPEN SOFTWARE (EXPERIMENTS AND DETECTORS)	18.2%	7,428	4,375
CULTURAL BENEFITS	9.7%	5,037	2,344
... FOR ONSITE VISITORS		4,807	2,242
... FOR ONLINE VISITORS		229	102
NET PRESENT VALUE (MCHF)			4,071
BENEFIT / COST RATIO			1.20

This table does not include the additional benefits that are explained in the main report.

Summary

This report details the data, assumptions, methodologies, and outcomes of a comprehensive socio-economic impact analysis for the first phase of the **FCC research infrastructure - the FCC-ee lepton collider**, including environmental externalities. It builds upon an initial version of the socio-economic impact assessment - conducted between 2020 and 2023 - which focused on an FCC-ee design with two experiments and was limited to assessing core cost and benefit pathways. A subsequent study - carried out between September 2024 and February 2025 - provided a complementary analysis based on a revised FCC-ee configuration including four experiments, an updated cost structure and project schedule. It refined the cost and benefit estimates from the previous assessment on the basis of updated data and assumptions and expanded the scope to encompass broader socio-economic effects and environmental externalities, both positive and negative. The findings of this latest study are presented in this report. They may be further updated at a later stage as the infrastructure design continues to

evolve. Indeed, this report should be considered a step in an **ongoing appraisal, continuously informing and supporting the project's design and implementation.**

The analysis spans the entire lifecycle of FCC-ee, encompassing its design, construction, operation, and gradual energy upgrade phases, with an assumed duration of 41 years from 2024 (first year of analysis) to 2064 (final year of data analysis).

Some features of the proposed infrastructure have the potential to support two particle colliders in sequence: the FCC-ee and the FCC-hh (Future Hadron Collider). However, due to the very long timespan associated with this integrated programme, this study adopts a precautionary approach by focusing solely on the first phase, specifically the construction of the FCC-ee. To address this limitation, the residual value of FCC-ee assets at the end of their operational life has been calculated and presented as an additional potential benefit, with the possibility of being transferred as a legacy to the FCC-hh, should it be built.

In evaluating the FCC-ee project, both costs and benefits are expressed incrementally in comparison to a scenario where the project is not implemented. In this counterfactual scenario, the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) would continue its operation until its anticipated end of life, and no new particle-collider would be constructed at CERN. CERN would continue its operation, exploiting the existing particle accelerators and some experimental infrastructures. This approach is designed to capture the "net" change, focusing on causally related effects that can be specifically attributed to the FCC-ee project.

The methodological approach is based on the latest literature and empirical research on the economic quantification of impacts associated with research infrastructures, and on the ESFRI recommendations for the long-term sustainability of research infrastructures.

Error! Reference source not found.**he table above summarises the results of this analysis, highlighting the expected costs and benefits from the implementation of the FCC-ee.** These estimates are based on the FCC-ee design at the time of the analysis, with conservative assumptions applied throughout. Further research can be carried out to estimate sensitivity of the assumptions and the uncertainties of the results, for instance using Monte Carlo simulation.

The FCC-ee is conceived as a design-to-cost project, with a total capital investment of approximately **16.2 billion CHF** (including the ttbar radiofrequency system, not discounted). This figure encompasses feasibility studies, civil construction works, creation of technical infrastructures, all particle accelerators (injectors, booster and collider) and all investment costs (including in-kind) related to the four experiment detectors.

Operation costs – amounting to a total of about **21 billion CHF** (over 19 years, not discounted) - include the costs of CERN staff and personnels of the collaborations, irrespective of the institutions employing them but based on their actual dedication to the project, as well as all expenses (both in-kind and outflows) that are needed for running the experiments and operating and maintaining the FCC-ee research infrastructure throughout the entire project duration (e.g. electricity, water, spares and human resources for maintenance and repair). Specifically, **personnel costs** amount to 16.8 billion CHF (over 37 years, not discounted), including the expenses associated to around 258,000 person-years over the entire FCC-ee lifecycle (2024–2064), covering design, construction, operation, and data analysis. The peak workforce is expected to exceed 15,000 individuals in 2060 (headcount). This diverse group includes scientists, engineers, technicians, administrative staff, doctoral and postdoctoral researchers, as well as undergraduate and Master's students, and apprentices. Of the total personnel, approximately 11% will work on particle accelerators and technical infrastructures, while the remaining 89% will focus on detectors and experimental physics (many of them for part time, e.g., because of teaching duties elsewhere). The **other costs** amount to 4.4 billion CHF (not discounted), which is equivalent to a yearly average of 232 million CHF annually over the FCC-ee's operation, from commissioning to the end of its operational phase.

The noteworthy **negative environmental externalities** of the FCC-ee project have been assessed. These include greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions expected to be generated during both the construction of the tunnel and surface sites, as well as during the operation phase. Other externalities related to the construction phase include noise from site preparation, shaft construction, and underground excavation, changes in land use that could impact biodiversity and ecosystems, as well as air pollution, GHG emissions, and congestion caused by the transportation of excavated material by trucks. Additionally, ionizing radiation from particle beam collisions and radioactive waste generated during the operation of the FCC-ee have been considered. The total cost of these environmental externalities is estimated to be around **653 million CHF** (not discounted), with GHG emissions representing the largest share (97%).

On the benefit side, the analysis focuses on the direct benefits currently known and foreseeable based on past factual evidence, particularly from the LHC project.

The first impact pathway assessed is the value (estimated at production cost) from **scientific content production**. It stems from the publication flow generated by scientists and engineers engaged in the collider and its experiments, resulting in diverse scientific products, ranging from journal articles and working papers to conference proceedings and presentations. These products can have a lasting impact, extending beyond the High-Energy Physics community, potentially influencing other knowledge domains, and addressing broader societal challenges. Scientometric techniques were employed to estimate scientific production impact and its propagation from the FCC-ee project. The methodology involved analysing historical patterns observed in comparable high-energy physics research programs like Tevatron, LEP, and LHC. The economic concepts of "opportunity cost" and "value of time" were employed to determine the marginal social value of scientific products, with adjustments to account for large co-authorship practices of international collaborations. This approach considered the time spent by individuals in producing these outputs and valued it based on their average hourly salaries. This method was applied to estimate the social value of scientific products produced by researchers directly involved in the research program (tier 0 products), those citing the initial tier 0 knowledge (tier 1 products), and products citing tier 1 outputs (tier 2 products). Over 38 000 scientific products are expected to be directly produced by researchers within the FCC-ee project, with an additional 500 000 products likely to be impacted through citations until the year 2083. By assuming that scientists collaborating on the project spend 55% of their time on research and scientific output, and that 22% of this effort is dedicated to FCC-related products, the estimated benefit from scientific production is approximately 6.5 billion CHF (not discounted). This valuation accounts for the diminishing value of tier 1 and tier 2 products compared to tier 0 products, as knowledge propagates through waves of production and the initial input from FCC-ee progressively diminishes.

The second impact pathway under consideration is the **value of early career researcher training**, which reflects FCC-ee's role in transferring knowledge, fostering skills development, and building capacities for individuals actively engaged in the research infrastructure program throughout its lifecycle. This analysis specifically evaluated the benefits accrued by apprentices, trainees, technical students, doctoral students, post-doctoral researchers, and associated personnel up to a cut-off age of 30. The analysis did not include the training value for other highly qualified personnel, temporary labour, and contracted works as well as for professionals that move from the project into other industrial domains. The benefit has been quantified by estimating the lifelong career development improvements for participants upon entering the labour market after gaining a working experience within the research program. Previous studies, further validated through a survey involving approximately 2 600 individuals, indicate that the lifetime salary benefit for an early-stage researcher works at FCC-ee would range from a minimum of 2% to a maximum of 10% for the average period of stay within the research infrastructure (3.78 years). The total socio-economic benefit is assessed at around 20.7 billion CHF (not discounted).

The third impact pathway explores the benefits generated by the project for the **industry**. This encompasses advantages for supplier companies engaged in the design, construction, and operation of the new research infrastructure. The benefit stems from increased financial performance of the suppliers resulting from the knowledge gained through close collaboration with the research infrastructure. This knowledge, in turn, contributes to the creation and improvement of new processes, products, and services that suppliers can leverage in other markets and domains. A profit multiplier has been determined, ranging from 1.96 for procurement with low or moderate technology intensity levels to 3.09 for procurement with high technology intensity levels. Applying this multiplier to the capital expenditure, the social benefits of technology procurement are estimated at 17.6 billion CHF (not discounted).

The fourth impact pathway relates to **free and open simulation software** that are likely to be required by FCC-ee for the detectors and data analysis. The socio-economic impacts arising from a new or significantly upgraded detector simulation software, with potential applicability beyond high-energy physics, were estimated (building on previous work for the LHC) as the cost that external users would save by adopting the software made freely available by CERN and other contributors. The estimated value stands at 7.4 billion CHF (not discounted).

The fifth impact pathway pertains to engagement of laypeople. Such kind of activities are directly linked to laypeople interest for scientific research, the technologies employed for this research, and the operations involved in designing and running particle accelerators and experiments. For the purposes of this study, the focus was put on on-site visitors and online/social media users. The impact of these activities was estimated based on actual observations of the LHC programme, measured in terms of increased awareness, interest, and understanding of science by members of society, collectively referred to as "**cultural benefit**". It is estimated that CERN will welcome about 19 million visitors between 2024-2064 period out of which 5.5 million will be attracted by FCC-ee. The benefit for on-site visitors was estimated using the travel cost method, which incorporates the costs borne by visitors to travel to CERN and FCC, the economic value of time spent traveling, along with any local expenditure connected to their visit based on an actual survey carried out over one year at CERN. This benefit is estimated (by the established travel cost approach) at 4.8 billion CHF (not discounted). For virtual visitors engaged through CERN-managed webpages and social media, the benefit was estimated based on the "opportunity cost of time". After estimating the volume of online visits directly associated to the FCC project and valuing the time spent during these visits, the benefit is estimated at 229 million CHF (not discounted). In total, the cultural benefits quantified in this analysis amount to 5 billion CHF (not discounted).

To aggregate the value of measured benefits and compare them with costs, a **Social Discount Rate (SDR)** was estimated specifically for the FCC-ee project. This project-specific rate accounts for the level of development and preferences for consumption and investments in countries contributing to the CERN budget and the very long duration of the project. The assumed SDR value is 2.8 % (close to rates adopted by guidelines of some EU institutions).

Applying the SDR to the benefits, a **total present value of benefits of 24 billion CHF** has been determined. Comparing this value to the 20 billion CHF present value of all costs (capital, operational and environmental costs) yields a **positive net present value of 4 billion CHF**. The **benefit/cost ratio is 1.20**, indicating that the so far quantifiable socio-economic benefits exceed costs by 20%. These findings suggest a positive net contribution of the FCC-ee project to societal well-being. It serves to demonstrate the long-term social profitability of the proposed new scientific research infrastructure.

The analysis conducted so far has identified costs and benefits which are likely to materialise from the implementation of FCC-ee as it is currently designed. Additional benefits may arise if further planning, integration, and appropriate contextual conditions are incorporated into the project design. However, due to uncertainties at this stage, these benefits are not included in the net present value and benefit/cost

ratio calculations presented in **Error! Reference source not found.**, which are prudent and conservative as a baseline. Potential additional benefits include the residual value of FCC-ee assets, assuming the subsequent FCC-hh project is developed. Moreover, the following potential positive environmental externalities have been identified: the provision of excess clean electricity to society resulting from the voluntary goal of supplying the FCC-ee with renewable energy, the ecosystem benefits from mitigation actions aimed at reducing negative environmental impacts, and the savings resulting from the use of heat recovery. Other expected ICT benefits include the development of innovative software (e.g., free digital platform inspired by the experience of the current ones, such as Zenodo and Indico) as well as industrial impacts through the development of spinoffs. Local impacts have also been explored. These include benefits from the reuse of waste heat (e.g., avoided costs of purchasing energy for heating from conventional energy sources such as oil, wood, gas, and electricity), enhanced safety due to emergency preparedness and intervention framework required by FCC-ee at both underground and surface levels, territorial benefits for the host countries (France and Switzerland) generated during the construction and operation phases of the FCC-ee, and regional benefits for all countries through procurement activity across the entire project life cycle.

After presenting the results of this analysis, item by item in terms of costs and benefits, this report concludes with a set of recommendations derived from the findings. The purpose of these recommendations is to ensure that the benefits can be monitored and regularly reported, allowing the updated findings to be integrated into the infrastructure's design, construction, and operation phases.

Conclusions

The socio-economic impact analysis conducted on the Future Circular Collider electron-positron (FCC-ee) has revealed numerous benefit potentials across various domains. The **total present value of quantified socio-economic benefits associated with the FCC-ee research infrastructures has been conservatively estimated at 24 billion CHF**. The core benefits quantified include pathways:

- The value of scientific products produced by scientists, engineers, and researchers, generating additional knowledge through citations;
- Positive impacts on supplier companies;
- Development of openly accessible simulation software;
- Training opportunities and salary increases for early-career researchers involved in the FCC-ee project;
- Impacts generated by on-site and online visitors.

These benefits have been appraised through a conservative methodology, drawing on the current understanding of the project, insights garnered from analogous past research infrastructures, and socio-economic impact analyses. Data collected between 2020 and 2025 has played a crucial role in shaping the new estimations for FCC-ee. To ensure a comprehensive perspective, data gathering efforts included over 16,000 respondents through online surveys, plus large sets of secondary data (such as on procurement orders, publications, etc).

On the costs side, investments and operational costs have been estimated on the basis of the current concept. Noteworthy negative externalities stemming from the project's construction (e.g. the consumption of agricultural land, the greenhouse gas footprint) have also been included into the analysis.

The core quantified benefits of the FCC-ee project exceed its total costs—associated with the design, construction, and operation—by a factor of 1.20, resulting in a net positive socio-economic impact. These findings highlight the project's potential benefits not only for the scientific community but for society as a whole, reinforcing its long-term sustainability.

These results reflect the likely costs and benefits based on current knowledge. Further sensitivity and uncertainty analysis, for instance based on Monte Carlo simulation can provide insight into the

dependency of the net present value on key influencing factors, and determine the minimum threshold at which the benefit-to-cost ratio reaches a break-even point with high confidence.

Additional potential benefits have been identified and explored to some extent but were not included in the quantified results due to their current uncertainty, even if some of them are potentially significant, particularly if the FCC-hh will be implemented. Their realisation depends on dedicated planning, integration, and suitable contextual conditions being incorporated into the project's design. Moreover, this analysis intentionally excludes attempts to quantify the unpredictable societal impacts of knowledge generated by the science mission.

This document may be updated over time to reflect ongoing refinements in infrastructure design. It should be regarded as part of a living appraisal that continuously informs and supports the project's development. It serves as a tool for decision-making, user engagement, risk mitigation, and enhancing the social acceptability of the FCC-ee project.

Recommendations

This study showed that a break-even of socio-economic costs and benefits (not to be confused with financial flows) can be achieved by the FCC-ee with the impact pathways documented so far. However, the potential can only be fully exploited if a continuous tracking of socio-economic impacts is integrated into the infrastructure's design, construction and operation phases. To achieve this objective, nine recommendations have been formulated.

1) The FCC programme should allocate personnel and material resources for the impact identification, design, planning, implementation, monitoring and assessment process to help fully leveraging the impact potentials and making FCC a socio-economically sustainable endeavour.

This personnel needs to be empowered to be able that the results of the impact assessment and the impact generation recommendations are indeed considered in the design where appropriate, that they are implemented and that the continuous, systematic monitoring and analysis is carried out with the help of all participating project members. This requires that socio-economic impact assessment is implemented as a cross-cutting activity across the entire organisation, with the direct involvement of the highest possible managerial level and reporting directly to CERN's key stakeholder, the Council. This approach is expected to secure the sustainability and effectiveness of the process, as well as help enhance project acceptance among financially contributing countries.

2) Concerning the impacts generated by scientific products, the FCC programme should encourage that scientific and engineering works are published via "gold open access" channels (as opposed to "self-publishing") and reputable outlets (not just to depositing information in preprint servers). This ensures proper identification of works for tracking purposes and increases their likelihood of uptake.

This socio-economic impact assessment study has revealed challenges in identifying all scientific outputs associated with the research infrastructure activities. It is essential to track the scientific production of researchers involved in experiments and monitor citations across papers and other scientific products. However, scientific outputs lacking proper unique digital identifiers and citation references, as it is often the case with workshop proceedings and presentations available in platforms like Indico, cannot be adequately identified and considered for socio-economic valuation. These types of outputs should, whenever possible, be replaced or supplemented by citable reports or papers. Establishing strategic partnerships with leading publishers, as exemplified by the SCOAP3 project, is a suitable approach to assure the presence of citable publications. Open access platforms used for dissemination could integrate download, citation and reference tracking, if they do not already offer those functions (e.g. Zenodo and ArXiv seems to lack part of these functions). Furthermore, additional

research is necessary to expand monitoring and tracking of scientific content beyond scientific and engineering articles and presentations to include books to better understand the societal uptake of knowledge acquisition within the FCC programme. Finally, a better understanding of co-authorship practices in HEP large collaborations and their actual representation of the scientists' effort in publishing, would provide insights for refining and advancing the current methodology for the economic valuation of scientific output based on the marginal cost of production.

3) Concerning the value of training, the FCC programme should foresee a framework to monitor the career paths of people after they leave CERN, to facilitate the analysis of future career developments.

Every individual contributing to the FCC project for a minimum duration should be encouraged, on a voluntary basis, to engage in a comprehensive monitoring programme. Thanks to mechanisms to reconnect with them periodically, this initiative would entail long-term follow-up and periodic collection of a set of basis information on their current work position.

4) To ensure the effective analysis of industrial spillovers generated during project implementation, the FCC program should incorporate systematic monitoring of the economic impacts on suppliers resulting from procurement actions over multi-year periods.

Given that these effects may not manifest immediately and can extend beyond the duration of the procurement contract, it is crucial to obtain feedback from the involved companies. This necessitates the establishment of a comprehensive procurement monitoring framework that facilitates ongoing engagement. Such a framework should include provisions for storing information on the individuals initially involved in the contract, enabling periodic follow-up after the contract's conclusion. Additionally, it should facilitate the collection of essential information regarding the spillover effects generated by the procurement experience with CERN on the company.

This can be achieved through mechanisms such as short online surveys designed to gather pertinent data. By implementing this approach, the FCC program can gain valuable insights into the long-term economic impacts of its procurement activities, fostering continuous improvement and enhancing collaboration with industry partners.

5) Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) have been identified as a key impact pathway that should be better leveraged through targeted transition actions to society, accompanied by systematic monitoring of uptake.

CERN and the FCC represent a globally unparalleled environment for the development of software and platforms to serve the needs of global collaborations, which is in high demand across societal and industrial sectors, too. By identifying the specific requirements of such collaborations and initiating dedicated development projects, the potential for widespread adoption beyond the FCC project can be created. Examples include communication (both one-to-one and one-to-many), file sharing, information management, remote operation, cybersecurity, data storage, distributed computing and data processing. CERN and the member states should ensure that the developed technologies are accessible to users outside the high-energy and particle physics community, free of charge, while also guaranteeing long-term maintenance and improvement. This requires making software and tools available on platforms that support download and installation tracking.

6) With respect to the impact of spin-off companies, there is a need to establish a systematic method for tracking companies founded by former participants in the FCC programme, monitoring their evolution over time, and assessing their economic value.

The establishment of new companies leveraging knowledge acquired through the FCC programme represents an important societal benefit. Notably, spin-offs often emerge from participants'

amalgamation of different skills and experiences, rather than the direct exploitation of a single licensed technology. In particular, the technologies developed in collaborative R&D projects cannot be attributed to CERN alone and CERN does not track the technologies of collaboration partners. However, to accurately gauge the economic and societal benefits generated, a voluntary, systematic tracking mechanism is essential. This tracking framework should facilitate a comprehensive assessment of the impact of spin-off companies. It could include the establishment of a centralised database to record information about spin-off companies (such as their founders, country, industry sector, products/services offered), and the possibility to periodically contact them to provide updates on their companies' progress.

7) Concerning the cultural impacts, the study revealed the relevance of economic benefits due to on site visitors. To ensure a sustainable monitoring of this impact pathway, CERN and the FCC collaboration should establish a unified framework to continuously collect essential data on visitor to CERN's exhibition centres, the experiments and any other relevant visit site.

A systematic tracking mechanism for visitors is indeed necessary to accurately report on the effects of on-site visitors. Visitors should be requested to provide a small set of basic information, including their country of origin, mode of transport to Geneva, main purpose of the visit, duration of stay, visitor spending, and feedback on the exhibitions and the visit sites (e.g. their level of satisfaction). By implementing this monitoring framework, it will be possible to effectively track and evaluate the cultural impact of on-site visitors, as well as enabling continual enhancement of visitor experiences.

8) Reduction or mitigation of negative externalities should be prioritised as part of a comprehensive effort of reducing the environmental impact of large scientific investment programmes.

Identifying and analysing environmental benefits is crucial for the social acceptability of scientific research and achieving a net-zero balance. The FCC study management team has begun assessing potential negative environmental impacts while also exploring the benefits of renewable energy sources, waste heat reuse, and the repurposing of excavated materials. As the project continues to evolve, this assessment must be updated accordingly to reflect new developments. Moreover, research and collaboration with project stakeholders, economists, and environmental experts may provide additional insights. This will be instrumental in understanding and mitigating potential adverse effects associated with the implementation of the FCC program, ensuring sustainability and the responsible use of natural resources.

9) Continuous monitoring of the public awareness and acceptance of major science investments is important to sense the expectations of funders, ultimately the taxpayers. This approach should be further intensified through surveys conducted in all potential funding countries and regularly repeated to enhance our understanding of how social acceptance can not only be maintained but also be improved.

A framework for streamlining this process has been developed within this project, enabling the activity to continue with only marginal additional resources. Expanding data collection to additional countries, beyond those already surveyed, can provide insights into the factors influencing the people's perception on the FCC programme. The findings should not be regularly shared with CERN management and the Council and summarised for broader dissemination to all stakeholders, including the public, through channels such as CERN's social media platforms and its main websites.